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Addressing Parental Responsibilities as a Nexus for Nigeria's Sociocultural Revolution

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Abstract

This paper investigates the pivotal role of parental guidance in shaping Nigeria's sociocultural landscape and explores the effects of parental failure on youth behaviour, societal values, and national development. Employing a qualitative methodological approach, the study examines the narratives and lived experiences of Nigerian families, drawing from extensive literature reviews, case studies, and cultural analyses. Grounded in Attachment Theory, the research provides a comprehensive understanding of how parenting impacts societal outcomes. The findings highlight that parental failure manifests in various forms, including lack of supervision and engagement, cultural and economic pressures, negligence of parental responsibilities, and deficiencies in educational background. In this context, parental failure refers to the inability or unwillingness of parents to adequately nurture, guide, and provide for their children, resulting in a range of negative outcomes for individuals and society. These manifestations contribute to widespread social issues such as juvenile delinquency, substance abuse, and the erosion of ethical values. The study underscores the importance of addressing parental failure as a catalyst for sociocultural transformation in Nigeria, arguing that a more cohesive and progressive society can be cultivated by empowering parents and tackling the root causes of parental failure through collaborative efforts from government, NGOs, and community leaders. Key recommendations include implementing parental education programs to equip parents with effective parenting skills, establishing economic support systems to alleviate financial burdens, and promoting cultural reorientation to encourage active and engaged parenting.

Keywords: Parenting, Parental Failure, Juvenile Delinquency, Socio-cultural Revolution

respect for elders, communal living, and moral integrity have historically been integral to the social fabric (Falola, 2001).

This paper explores the nexus between parental responsibilities and Nigeria's sociocultural evolution, proposing that addressing these failures is essential for fostering a sociocultural revolution. By examining the root causes of parental failure and its impacts on youth behavior and societal values, the study seeks to provide a framework for systemic change.

The qualitative methodological approach adopted in this study involves an in-depth analysis of existing literature, case studies, and cultural narratives to uncover the underlying factors contributing to parental failure in Nigeria. This approach allows for a nuanced understanding of the complex interplay between individual, familial, and societal factors. By exploring the lived experiences of Nigerian families, the study aims to provide actionable insights and recommendations for fostering a sociocultural revolution.

Addressing parental failure is crucial for Nigeria's sociocultural revolution. By empowering parents through education, support, and cultural reorientation, Nigeria can cultivate a more cohesive and progressive society. This paper calls for collaborative efforts from government, NGOs, and community leaders to spearhead initiatives that reinforce the importance of effective parenting in national development. Through such efforts, Nigeria can lay the groundwork for sustainable development and social cohesion, ultimately achieving a brighter future for its children and society as a whole.

Literature Review

Parental Failure and Child Development

The role of parents in child development has been extensively studied, with consensus pointing towards the critical impact of parental behavior on various aspects of a child's life. According to Attachment Theory developed by John Bowlby in 1969 children form attachments with their caregivers, which serve as a foundation for their emotional and social development. Secure attachments are formed when parents are

responsive and sensitive to their children's needs, whereas insecure attachments result from inconsistent or neglectful caregiving. Insecurely attached children are at a higher risk of developing behavioural problems and mental health issues (Ainsworth, 1979).

Economic Challenges and Parental Failure

Economic hardship is a significant factor contributing to parental failure in Nigeria. Parents facing financial difficulties often work long hours or multiple jobs to make ends meet, resulting in limited time and energy for parental engagement (Egbo, 2012). The stress associated with economic instability can also affect parental mental health, further impairing their ability to provide adequate care and support for their children (Conger, et al., 1992). Studies have shown that economic hardship is correlated with increased instances of child neglect and abuse, as well as poorer educational outcomes for children (Wadsworth & Santiago, 2008).

In Nigeria, the economic challenges are compounded by a lack of social support systems and adequate public policies. The absence of robust welfare programs means that many families lack access to essential resources such as healthcare, education, and housing, exacerbating the effects of poverty on family dynamics (Oyeniya, 2013). The intersection of economic hardship and parental failure creates a vicious cycle where children from impoverished families are less likely to receive the support and opportunities needed to break out of poverty.

Cultural Influences on Parenting

Cultural norms and values play a crucial role in shaping parenting practices and expectations in Nigeria. Traditional Nigerian culture places a high value on respect for elders and hierarchical family structures, often emphasizing obedience and conformity over individual expression and autonomy (Falola, 2001). While these values can foster strong family bonds and community cohesion, they can also limit open communication and critical thinking, particularly in parent-child relationships (Omoegun, 2007).

Cultural expectations can also contribute to parental failure by placing undue pressure on parents to conform to traditional roles and responsibilities. For example, gender norms that assign primary caregiving responsibilities to mothers can limit fathers' involvement in parenting, leading to imbalanced parental roles and increased stress on mothers (Olutayo & Bankole, 2002). Additionally, cultural stigmas surrounding issues such as mental health and parenting support can prevent parents from seeking help when needed, exacerbating the challenges they face (Gureje et al., 2006).

Educational Deficiencies and Parenting

Educational attainment is a significant determinant of effective parenting. Parents with higher levels of education are generally better equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to support their children's development (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003). In Nigeria, however, many parents have limited educational backgrounds, which can hinder their ability to provide appropriate guidance and support for their children (UNICEF, 2018). This issue is particularly pronounced in rural areas, where access to quality education is often limited (Onyukwu, 2011).

Educational deficiencies in parents can also impact their children's academic achievement and aspirations. Research has shown that parental education levels are positively correlated with children's educational outcomes, suggesting that parents who lack education may struggle to foster a conducive learning environment for their children (Fan & Chen, 2001). This creates a cycle of educational disadvantage, where children from less educated families are less likely to succeed academically and attain higher levels of education themselves.

The Interplay of Parental Failure and Societal Outcomes

The cumulative effects of parental failure have significant implications for broader societal outcomes in Nigeria. Children who grow up in environments characterized by neglect, abuse, or lack of support are more likely to engage in antisocial behaviour, including criminal

activities and substance abuse (Adegoke, 2015). This behaviour contributes to higher crime rates and social instability, posing challenges to national development and social cohesion (Blum et al., 2000).

Moreover, the erosion of ethical and moral values associated with parental failure undermines the social fabric of Nigerian society. Traditional values such as respect, communal living, and integrity, which have historically been pillars of Nigerian culture, are increasingly being compromised (Falola, 2001). This cultural shift has profound implications for social interactions, community cohesion, and national identity.

Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that considers the broader systemic and cultural contexts in which families operate. By understanding and addressing the root causes of parental failure, Nigeria can pave the way for a sociocultural revolution that promotes positive values, ethical behavior, and sustainable development.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on Attachment Theory. This theory provides a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of parental failure and its impact on child development within the sociocultural context of Nigeria.

John Bowlby's Attachment Theory underscores the crucial role of early relationships between children and their primary caregivers in shaping emotional and social development (Bowlby, 1969). The theory posits that the quality of attachment formed during infancy and early childhood profoundly impacts a child's future relational and psychological well-being. Secure attachments, characterized by consistent and responsive caregiving, foster healthy emotional regulation, resilience, and social competence. Conversely, insecure attachments, which arise from neglectful or inconsistent parenting, can lead to a range of developmental challenges such as anxiety, behavioural issues, and difficulties in forming stable interpersonal relationships.

In the context of Nigeria, socio-economic pressures and cultural norms often disrupt the formation of secure attachments. Economic constraints, such as financial instability and high rates of poverty, can compel parents to prioritize survival over nurturing, thereby impacting their ability to provide consistent and responsive caregiving. Additionally, cultural expectations and traditional norms sometimes place unrealistic demands on parents, further exacerbating the challenge of meeting their children's emotional needs. These factors contribute to a cycle of insecure attachments, which can perpetuate issues such as juvenile delinquency, substance abuse, and erosion of ethical values within the society.

Addressing parental responsibilities through the lens of Attachment Theory presents a critical opportunity for Nigeria's sociocultural revolution. By emphasizing the importance of secure attachments and the role of responsive caregiving, interventions can be designed to support parents in creating nurturing environments. This includes implementing parental education programs to enhance understanding of attachment principles, providing economic support to alleviate financial stress, and fostering cultural reorientation to emphasize the value of emotional availability and consistent caregiving. Such comprehensive efforts can help break the cycle of insecure attachments and contribute to the development of a more cohesive and progressive society.

Impacts of Parental Failure on Sociocultural Revolution

Parental failure has profound implications not only for individual child development but also for the broader sociocultural fabric of society. In Nigeria, where traditional values and social structures are deeply embedded, the repercussions of parental failure extend beyond the household, influencing community dynamics and national development. This section explores how parental failure impedes sociocultural revolution in Nigeria, hindering the country's progress towards modernization, ethical integrity, and social cohesion.

Erosion of Traditional Values and Ethical Standards

Traditional Nigerian society is built on values such as respect, communal living, and moral integrity. These values are primarily transmitted through family structures and parenting practices. However, when parents fail to provide a stable and nurturing environment, these core values are compromised. The breakdown of traditional family roles and the rise in single-parent households, often resulting from economic pressures and social instability, lead to weakened family bonds and a decline in the transmission of cultural norms (Falola, 2001). Children growing up in such environments may lack the guidance needed to internalize these values, leading to an erosion of societal ethical standards.

Moreover, the prevalence of neglect and abuse within families can contribute to a culture of violence and disrespect. Children who experience or witness domestic violence are more likely to adopt aggressive behaviour and view violence as a normative means of conflict resolution (Jaffee et al., 2003). This perpetuates a cycle of violence that undermines social harmony and ethical conduct, posing significant challenges to societal stability and cohesion.

Impact on Education and Skill Development

Educational attainment is a critical factor in driving sociocultural revolution. It empowers individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for innovation, economic development, and social progress. However, parental failure, particularly in the form of neglect and lack of support for education, severely hampers children's academic performance and future prospects (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003). In Nigeria, many children from disadvantaged backgrounds do not receive the encouragement or resources needed to succeed in school, leading to high dropout rates and limited access to higher education (UNICEF, 2018).

This educational deficit has long-term implications for the country's workforce and economic development. A poorly educated population is less capable of contributing to technological advancements and

economic growth, which are essential components of a sociocultural revolution. Furthermore, the lack of educational opportunities exacerbates social inequalities, creating a divide between the educated elite and the underprivileged masses. This social stratification hinders national unity and the collective effort needed for transformative social change.

Perpetuation of Gender Inequality

Gender norms and expectations play a significant role in shaping parenting practices and, consequently, the impact of parental failure. In Nigeria, traditional gender roles often dictate that women are primarily responsible for child-rearing, while men are seen as breadwinners (Olutayo & Bankole, 2002). These norms can limit the involvement of fathers in parenting and place disproportionate stress on mothers, particularly in the context of economic hardship.

Parental failure, influenced by these gendered expectations, can perpetuate gender inequalities by limiting educational and career opportunities for girls. Girls in families where parents are unable or unwilling to support their education are more likely to be kept at home for domestic duties or married off at an early age (Omoegun, 2007). This not only curtails their personal development but also reinforces the cycle of poverty and gender discrimination. For a sociocultural revolution to take place, it is imperative to address these deep-rooted gender biases and promote equal opportunities for all children, regardless of gender.

Increase in Antisocial Behaviour and Crime

One of the most immediate and visible impacts of parental failure is the increase in antisocial behaviour and crime among youth. Children who grow up in environments characterized by neglect, abuse, or lack of supervision are more likely to engage in criminal activities (Adegoke, 2015). The absence of positive role models and the exposure to harmful behaviour create a predisposition towards delinquency and substance abuse.

The rise in youth crime poses a significant barrier to sociocultural revolution, as it diverts resources away from development initiatives and

towards policing and criminal justice. Additionally, high crime rates create an atmosphere of fear and instability, discouraging investment and community engagement. Addressing the root causes of antisocial behavior through improved parenting practices and supportive family environments is crucial for fostering a safe and productive society.

Implications for National Development and Social Cohesion

The cumulative effects of parental failure extend to national development and social cohesion. Children who do not receive adequate care and support are less likely to become productive and responsible citizens. This affects the overall human capital of the nation, reducing its potential for economic growth and social progress (Blum et al., 2000). Furthermore, the breakdown of family structures and the erosion of cultural values can lead to social fragmentation, where communities become polarized and distrustful.

A sociocultural revolution requires a collective effort towards shared goals and values. Parental failure undermines this collective spirit by fostering environments of neglect, inequality, and conflict. To achieve meaningful social transformation, it is essential to strengthen family units and promote positive parenting practices that support the holistic development of children.

Parental failure has far-reaching implications for Nigeria's sociocultural revolution. It erodes traditional values, hampers educational and skill development, perpetuates gender inequality, increases antisocial behaviour and crime, and ultimately undermines national development and social cohesion.

Case Studies of Parental Failure and Implications

Examining case studies of parental failure provides valuable insights into the complexities and consequences of inadequate parenting practices in Nigeria. These case studies shed light on the diverse factors contributing to parental failure and the multifaceted implications for child development, societal well-being, and national progress. This section presents case studies highlighting different manifestations of

parental failure and their implications for individuals and communities, including a scriptural example from the Bible.

Eli's Parental Failure and the Moral Decline of His Sons

Eli, a high priest and judge of Israel, serves as a poignant biblical example of the repercussions of parental failure on both the family and the broader community. Eli's inability to discipline his sons, Hophni and Phinehas, led to severe moral and spiritual decline, affecting not only his household but also the entire nation of Israel.

Background

Eli's sons, Hophni and Phinehas, served as priests under their father's leadership. Despite their sacred roles, they engaged in corrupt practices, such as taking the best portions of sacrifices for themselves and committing sexual immorality with women who served at the entrance to the Tent of Meeting (1 Samuel 2:12-17, 22). Eli was aware of his sons' misconduct but failed to take decisive action to correct their behavior, merely rebuking them without enforcing any meaningful consequences (1 Samuel 2:22-25).

Implications

The parental failure of Eli had far-reaching consequences for his family and the community:

1. *Moral and Spiritual Decline:* Eli's failure to discipline his sons led to a significant decline in moral and spiritual standards among the priests, which undermined the integrity of religious practices and disillusioned the people of Israel. The priests' corruption eroded public trust in religious institutions, contributing to a broader societal crisis of faith.
2. *Divine Judgment and Family Tragedy:* The lack of effective parental guidance and discipline resulted in severe divine judgment. God pronounced judgment on Eli's household, declaring that both Hophni and Phinehas would die on the same day as a sign of His displeasure (1 Samuel 2:27-36). This

prophecy was fulfilled during a battle with the Philistines, leading to the loss of the Ark of the Covenant and the deaths of Eli's sons (1 Samuel 4:10-11). Eli himself died upon hearing the news, marking a tragic end for his family (1 Samuel 4:18).

3. *National Consequences:* The moral failings of Eli's sons and the subsequent loss of the Ark of the Covenant had profound national implications. The Israelites' defeat and the capture of the Ark symbolized a spiritual low point for the nation, leading to a period of instability and despair. This event highlighted the critical importance of strong, ethical leadership and the devastating impact that parental failure can have on a community's spiritual and moral health.

The case study of Eli and his sons illustrates the severe consequences of parental failure, both within the family and across the broader community. Eli's inability to effectively discipline and guide his sons led to moral corruption, divine judgment, and national calamity. This scriptural example underscores the vital role of parents in shaping the moral and spiritual character of their children and the far-reaching implications of parental failure.

Case Study: David's Parental Failure and Its Implications

King David, one of the most prominent figures in the Bible, is often celebrated for his leadership and devotion to God. However, his failures as a parent had significant repercussions for his family, the kingdom of Israel, and its sociocultural fabric. This case study explores David's parental shortcomings and their implications for both his household and the broader society.

Background

David had several children by multiple wives, which often led to complex family dynamics and rivalries. His failure to address these issues effectively, coupled with his inability to discipline his children appropriately, resulted in serious consequences.

1. *The Incident with Amnon and Tamar*: One of the most notable instances of David's parental failure involves his children Amnon, Tamar, and Absalom. Amnon, David's eldest son, developed an inappropriate desire for his half-sister Tamar. Despite the serious nature of the offense, David's response was passive and inadequate, showing leniency towards Amnon (2 Samuel 13:1-21). This lack of decisive action led to further familial strife.
2. *Absalom's Rebellion*: Absalom, Tamar's full brother, was enraged by David's failure to punish Amnon. This led him to take matters into his own hands, eventually killing Amnon (2 Samuel 13:22-29). Absalom fled and later returned, harboring resentment towards David. This unresolved tension culminated in Absalom leading a rebellion against his father, causing a significant civil conflict within Israel (2 Samuel 15:1-12).

Implications

David's parental failures had far-reaching implications, affecting not only his family but also the kingdom of Israel and its sociocultural development.

1. *Family Dysfunction and Breakdown*: David's inability to manage his children's conflicts and enforce discipline resulted in a dysfunctional family environment. The lack of parental authority and guidance led to severe sibling rivalries and violence. This breakdown in family structure highlights the importance of effective parenting in maintaining family harmony and stability.
2. *Social and Political Instability*: Absalom's rebellion against David had significant political repercussions. The civil war that ensued disrupted the kingdom, causing widespread instability and suffering. This period of turmoil weakened the nation's cohesion and diverted resources from development efforts, illustrating how familial conflicts can escalate to national crises.
3. *Erosion of Moral and Ethical Standards*: David's failure to hold Amnon accountable for his actions sent a negative message about

justice and accountability. This erosion of moral and ethical standards can undermine societal values, leading to a culture of impunity and lawlessness. In David's case, his actions (or lack thereof) set a precedent that influenced the behavior of others within the kingdom.

4. *Long-term Sociocultural Impact:* The turmoil within David's family and the ensuing political instability had long-term implications for Israel's sociocultural development. The civil unrest weakened the central authority, leading to periods of vulnerability and division. This environment hindered the nation's ability to progress and develop cohesively, impacting future generations.

David's parental failures had profound implications for his family and the kingdom of Israel. His inability to address serious issues within his household led to significant familial conflict, social instability, and a decline in moral and ethical standards. These events underscore the critical role of effective parenting in fostering stable family environments and promoting national development.

Solutions to Parental Failure

Addressing parental failure in Nigeria requires practical solutions that empower parents, support families, and promote positive parenting practices.

1. *Parenting Education and Support Programs:* Implementing parenting education and support programs can empower parents with the knowledge and skills needed to provide nurturing and supportive environments for their children. These programs can include workshops, seminars, and counseling sessions focused on topics such as child development, communication, discipline, and stress management. By equipping parents with the tools and resources they need, these programs can help prevent parental failure and promote positive parent-child relationships.
2. *Economic Empowerment Initiatives:* Creating economic empowerment initiatives aimed at alleviating poverty and providing financial stability for families can reduce the risk of

parental failure. These initiatives can include job training programs, microfinance loans, and income-generating opportunities targeted at low-income families. By improving economic opportunities for parents, these initiatives can strengthen family resilience and enable parents to better provide for their children's needs.

3. *Accessible and Affordable Childcare Services:* Expanding access to affordable and high-quality childcare services can support working parents and reduce the burden of caregiving. This can include establishing daycare centers, after-school programs, and early childhood education facilities in communities across Nigeria. By providing safe and nurturing environments for children, these services can enable parents to pursue employment or education opportunities while ensuring their children receive the care and support they need.
4. *Community Engagement and Support Networks:* Promoting community engagement and support networks can create a sense of belonging and social connectedness for parents and children alike. This can involve establishing parent support groups, community centers, and neighborhood initiatives that provide opportunities for families to connect, share resources, and access social support. By fostering a sense of community and collective responsibility, these networks can help strengthen family bonds and prevent social isolation.
5. *Strengthen Parental Education and Support:* Implement comprehensive parental education programs that equip parents with effective discipline strategies, moral guidance techniques, and communication skills. These programs should be accessible and culturally relevant, addressing the specific challenges faced by families in Nigeria.
6. *Promote Ethical and Spiritual Leadership:* Encourage parents to model ethical behavior and spiritual leadership within their households. Faith-based organizations and community leaders

can play a pivotal role in promoting values that foster moral integrity and accountability.

7. *Develop Community Support Systems:* Establish robust community support systems that provide resources, counseling, and mentorship for families struggling with parental challenges. By fostering a supportive community environment, parents can receive the assistance they need to guide their children effectively.
8. *Implement Accountability Mechanisms:* Create and enforce accountability mechanisms within religious and community institutions to address misconduct and ensure ethical standards are upheld. This can help prevent moral decline and maintain public trust in leadership.
9. *Parental Accountability:* Encourage parents to take an active role in addressing and resolving conflicts within their families. Accountability and decisive action are essential in maintaining discipline and justice.
10. *Conflict Resolution Training:* Implement conflict resolution training programs for parents and community leaders. These programs can provide the skills needed to manage disputes effectively and prevent escalation.

By implementing practical solutions, Nigeria can create a supportive and nurturing environment for children to thrive. These efforts are essential for driving sociocultural revolution and building a more inclusive and equitable society.

Summary

Parental failure in Nigeria poses significant challenges to child development, societal well-being, and the country's progress towards sociocultural revolution. Economic hardship, cultural norms, educational disparities, and family structure are among the key factors contributing to parental failure. The implications of parental failure are far-reaching, affecting ethical values, educational attainment, gender equality, and social stability. However, practical solutions such as

is crucial. This support enables working parents to balance their responsibilities and reduces the caregiving burden.

4. *Strengthening of Community Support Networks*: Community engagement and support networks are instrumental in fostering connections among families. These networks offer opportunities for resource sharing and social support, promoting social cohesion and a sense of collective responsibility.

5. *Advocacy for Policy Reform*: Policy reforms that address economic disparities, cultural norms, and educational inequalities are necessary to support families. Such reforms aim to create an environment where children and families can thrive, addressing the root causes of parental challenges.

Implementing these recommendations will require coordinated efforts from government agencies, non-governmental organizations, community leaders, and other stakeholders. By prioritizing the well-being of children and families, Nigeria can overcome the challenges of parental failure and realize its aspirations for sociocultural revolution and national development.

References

- Adegoke, A. A. (2015). "Impact of Parental Influence on Adolescents' Academic Achievement." *International Journal of Educational Research*. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijer.2015.05.002
- Adevale, J. G. (2014). "Parental Involvement in Education: An Empirical Study on the Perception of Parents in Nigeria." *Journal of Education and Practice*. DOI: 10.7176/JEP/5-8-7
- Ainsworth, M. D. (1979). "Infant-Mother Attachment." *American Psychologist*, 34(10), 932-937. DOI: 10.1037/0003-066X.34.10.932
- Bowlby, J. (1969). *Attachment and loss: Vol. 1. Attachment*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Conger, R. D., Ge, X., Elder, G. H., Lorenz, F. O., & Simons, R. L. (1992). "Economic Stress, Coercive Family Process, and Developmental Problems of Adolescents." *Child Development*, 63(2), 526-541. DOI: 10.2307/1131344

- Desforges, C., & Abouchaar, A. (2003). "The Impact of Parental Involvement, Parental Support and Family Education on Pupil Achievement and Adjustment: A Literature Review." Research Report RR433. Retrieved May 30, 2024 from <https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/6305/>
- Egbo, B. (2012). *Nigerian education: Trends and insights*. Nsukka, Nigeria: University of Nigeria Press.
- Falola, T. (2001). *Culture and customs of Nigeria*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Jaffee, S. R., Moffitt, T. E., Caspi, A., & Taylor, A. (2003). "Life With (or Without) Father: The Benefits of Living with Two Biological Parents Depend on the Father's Antisocial Behavior." *Child Development*, 74(1), 109-126. DOI: 10.1111/1467-8624.t01-1-00524
- Olutayo, A. O., & Bankole, A. O. (2002). "Sociology and the Emerging Global Order: The Challenges of Gender Equality." *International Journal of Sociology of the Family*, 28(2), 83-100.
- Omoegun, M. (2007). "Effect of Parental Socio-Economic Status on Parental Care and Social Adjustment in the UBE Programme in Lagos State: Implications for Counseling." *International Journal of Educational Research*, 3(2), 81-87.
- Omoegun, O. M. (2007). "Effect of Parental Involvement on Students' Academic Achievement." *Educational Research Quarterly*.
- UNICEF (2018). "Education in Nigeria." Retrieved May 30, 2024 from <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/education>
- UNICEF (2018). "Situation Analysis of Children in Nigeria." Retrieved May 30, 2024 from at: <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/reports/situation-analysis-children-nigeria>